

Sample preparation investigation to extract plastic additives in agricultural soil using UHPLC-MS/MS

Aristeidis S. Tsagkaris, Darina Dvorakova, Jana Pulkrabova*

Department of Food Analysis and Nutrition, Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology,
University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6 – Dejvice,
Prague, Czech Republic

Plastic additives (PAs) are chemicals blended with polymers during their production to improve the physicochemical properties of the final product. In the case of agricultural plastics (APs), certain plastic polymer types are widely used, e.g., polyolefins, containing antioxidants and light stabilizers to protect polymers against sunlight and/or ambient UV-radiation. Importantly, PAs are not covalently bound on the polymer matrix indicating their potential to leach into the environment. Considering that certain APs are directly applied into soil, namely, mulching films, and their waste mishandling, for example mulching film burying instead of collecting after use, PAs leaching into agricultural soil is highly probable, especially during AP degradation into micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) [1]. Thus, it is of utmost importance to monitor PAs derived by APs to study their fate in soil. In this study, we investigated different sample preparation strategies to extract 19 PAs from the complex soil matrix followed by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS). During the preliminary stage, the potential of plastic apparatus commonly used in the lab, for example centrifugal tubes or pipette tips, to contaminate the samples was evaluated and necessary steps were taken to avoid any background contamination. Following up, ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) and a binary extraction combining QuEChERS and UAE principles were tested in terms of extractant, extract clean-up (based on dispersive solid phase extraction) and preconcentration to increase method detectability. To monitor the effectiveness of the two strategies, trueness, repeatability, detectability and matrix effects were evaluated. Based on the acquired performance characteristics, the application of three different workflows was necessary to effectively measure the analytes, considering their diverse polarities ($-3 < \log P < 19$). In detail, aqueous UAE was proven the most efficient for polar analytes, such as dipentaerythriol, whilst UAE using hexane as the extractant achieved the best analytical performance for the analyte majority. Employing the binary extraction with ethyl acetate as the extractant was necessary to isolate Irganox 1024 and Irganox 1010, compounds that was not possible to detect without the phase separation and salting out induced by QuEChERS. All in all, effective PA extraction was achieved and validation experiments are underway to attain the completed performance characteristics for all methods.

Reference: [1] J.L.D Nelis et al, *The measurement of food safety and security risks associated with micro- and nanoplastic pollution*, 2023, TrAC, Vol. 161, 116993